

Mine Me but Don't Single Me Out: Supplementary Material

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Abstract. In this document, we provide the supplementary material for our paper. First, we present the proofs of privacy. Then, we list the selected event logs, their characteristics, and their descriptive statistics. Also, we list the anonymized event logs attached with the document as the result of the experiments.

Keywords: Process Mining · Privacy-Enhancing Technologies · Differential Privacy

1 Proof of Privacy

In this section, we prove that the proposed privacy mechanism and Algorithm 1 anonymize an event log so that the guessing advantage that an attacker gain after the disclosure of the event log would not exceed δ . Furthermore, we prove that the proposed method fulfills the requirements R1 and R2. As presented in the paper, the attacker has the following goals:

- h_1 : Has the individual been through a particular subtrace (prefix or suffix)? The output is a bit with a value $\in \{0, 1\}$ that represents yes or no.
- h_2 : What is the execution time of a particular activity that been executed for the individual? The output is a real value to be guessed with some precision.

1.1 Guessing Advantage

In this section, we prove that the adoption of the guessing advantage mechanism fulfills the requirement R2. Laud et al. [11,10] proposed an estimation of the posterior guessing probability. In our paper, we apply the results of Laud et al. [11,10] to the disclosure of the timestamp attribute of the event log.

Proposition 1 (Posterior Guessing Probability [11,10]). *The posterior guessing probability of an attribute ranging between 0 and r for a single individual after the disclosure of the timestamp attribute of an event log is bounded by*

$$P' \leq \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\epsilon \cdot r)^{\frac{1-P}{P}}} .$$

Proof. (Taken from [11,10]) An attacker has a prior knowledge $k(l)$ of part of the event log l . Using the equality $Pr[X = x] = \sum_{y \in Y} Pr[X = x, Y = y]$ and Bayesian formula $Pr[A, B] = Pr[A|B] \cdot Pr[B]$, we can rewrite

$$\begin{aligned}
P' &:= Pr[h(L) \in H_p \mid M_f(L) = M_f(l), k(L) = k(l)] \\
&= \frac{Pr[h(L) \in H_p, M_f(L) = M_f(l), k(L) = k(l)]}{Pr[M_f(L) = M_f(l), k(L) = k(l)]} \\
&= \frac{\sum_{l': h(l') \in H_p, k(l') = k(l)} Pr[M_f(l') = M_f(l)] \cdot Pr[L = l']}{\sum_{l': k(l) = k(l')} Pr[M_f(l') = M_f(l)] \cdot Pr[L = l']} \\
&= \frac{1}{1 + \frac{\sum_{l': h(l') \notin H_p, k(l') = k(l)} Pr[M_f(l') = M_f(l)] \cdot Pr[L = l']}{\sum_{l'': h(l'') \in H_p, k(l'') = k(l)} Pr[M_f(l'') = M_f(l)] \cdot Pr[L = l']}} ,
\end{aligned}$$

For an ϵ -DP mechanism M_f , since l' and l'' differ in one item due to the condition $k(l') = k(l) = k(l'')$, we have $\frac{Pr[M_f(l') = M_f(l)]}{Pr[M_f(l'') = M_f(l)]} \geq \exp(-\epsilon \cdot r)$, where r is the largest possible difference between two values of an attribute that the attacker is guessing. This gives us

$$\begin{aligned}
P' &\leq \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\epsilon \cdot r) \frac{\sum_{l': h(l') \notin H_p, k(l') = k(l)} Pr[L = l']}{\sum_{l'': h(l'') \in H_p, k(l'') = k(l)} Pr[L = l']}} \\
&= \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\epsilon \cdot r) \frac{Pr[h(L) \notin H_p, k(L) = k(l)]}{Pr[h(L) \in H_p, k(L) = k(l)]}} \\
&= \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\epsilon \cdot r) \frac{Pr[h(L) \notin H_p \mid k(L) = k(l)]}{Pr[h(L) \in H_p \mid k(L) = k(l)]}}
\end{aligned}$$

Putting P as in Definition 3.10, we get

$$P' \leq \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\epsilon \cdot r) \frac{1-P}{P}} . \quad (1)$$

□

Proposition 2. *The maximum possible ϵ that achieves the upper bound δ , w.r.t the particular attack model, and fulfills the requirement R2 is $\epsilon = \frac{-\ln\left(\frac{P}{1-P} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\delta+P} - 1\right)\right)}{r}$*

Proof. Given Definition 3.11, δ is the maximum guessing advantage probability after disclosing the attribute. Therefore,

$$P' - P \leq \delta . \quad (2)$$

Substituting Eq (1) into Eq (2), we can estimate the largest possible ϵ (the minimum amount of noise) that achieves the upper bound δ as

$$\epsilon = \frac{-\ln\left(\frac{P}{1-P} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\delta+P} - 1\right)\right)}{r} . \quad (3)$$

From Eq (3), the ϵ represents the maximum possible value for ϵ achieving the bound δ . Hence, we use Eq (3) to get the minimum possible noise to fulfill the requirement $R2$. \square

1.2 Contingency Table (CT)

In Definition 3.5, we defined the DAFSA transition Contingency table as a histogram of counts of DAFSA transitions. First, we estimate the privacy leakage through the contingency table.

Proposition 3. *Let M^{CT} be a mechanism that, for each count cell, samples (independently) noise from the Laplace distribution $Lap(1/\epsilon)$ and adds it to the count. Then, the level of DP w.r.t. change in a prefix/suffix of some trace of the underlying event log is:*

1. ϵ for a single count cell of the noisified CT;
2. $k \cdot \epsilon$ for the entire noisified CT, where k is the longest case length in the event log.

Proof. Suppose that we updated a prefix/suffix of a trace in the event log to become another prefix/suffix in the event log. Let us see how it affects the counts in the contingency table. However, each single count cell may change by at most ± 1 for each update step. Hence, the global sensitivity of a single count cell w.r.t. changing some prefix/suffix is 1. We can sample additive noise from distribution $Lap(1/\epsilon)$ and add it to a count cell to achieve ϵ -DP w.r.t. that count cell.

For the entire contingency table, a change in the frequency of a single case variant can affect at most k count cells (i.e., the count over the DAFSA transitions that represent that case variant), where k is the maximum case variant length in the event log. Hence, the global sensitivity is k , and we need to sample noise from $Lap(k/\epsilon)$ to achieve ϵ -DP. \square

Let us assume that we are given a desired upper bound δ on the attacker's advantage in guessing whether the target individual has prefix/suffix x or x' in the given event log, i.e., goal h_1 .

Proposition 4. *Let M^{CT} be a mechanism that, for each count cell, samples (independently) noise from the Laplace distribution $Lap(1/\epsilon)$ and adds it to the count. Let δ be the desired upper bound of the attacker succeeding in the goal h_1 . Then, it suffices to take*

$$\epsilon = -\ln \left(\frac{P}{1-P} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\delta+P} - 1 \right) \right),$$

where $P = \frac{1-\delta}{2}$.

Proof. Let P be the prior probability of guessing (i.e., without observing the output). We adopt the mechanism proposed by Laud et al. [11,10] to estimate

an upper bound on the difference between the posterior and the prior probability of guessing an attribute ranging between 0 and 1 ($r=1$) by

$$\delta = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\epsilon)^{\frac{1-P}{P}}} - P ,$$

which can be reversed to

$$\epsilon = -\ln \left(\frac{P}{1-P} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\delta+P} - 1 \right) \right) .$$

Laud et al. [11,10] estimate the prior knowledge P from the distribution of input values. However, the contingency table contains a count of values, which means the lack of distribution. Laud et al. [11,10] elaborate that, in case of the lack of distribution, we can estimate the value of P that minimizes the ϵ . We take the derivative of ϵ w.r.t. P , which yields $P = \frac{1-\delta}{2}$ as the prior knowledge for the contingency table counts.

We need to sample noise to achieve ϵ -DP. While $Lap(1/\epsilon)$ would be enough for a single count cell, for an entire table we would need $Lap(k/\epsilon)$ where k is the longest case length in the event log, as shown in Proposition 3. Can we do better?

Let us fix a single count cell. All correlated cells may provide additional information about the target cell. For example, suppose the target individual took part in an event B . In that case, it may follow that the individual took part in A even if the attacker does not see any frequency counts for A . This additional knowledge may increase P . However, we have already chosen the *worst-case* P for estimating the noise, regardless of any background knowledge that the attacker may get, including the related outputs. We note that if we used another prior knowledge estimation, then we would indeed require sampling noise from $Lap(k/\epsilon)$. \square

1.3 Correctness Proof of Algorithm 1 (Oversampling Algorithm)

We are interested in the leakage of a noisified event log. In order to translate the numerical noise, quantified by the DAFSA transitions (in CT), we use oversampling into the event log space. Let us prove that it provides the same level of privacy under certain circumstances.

We assume that the event log contains the three columns: Case ID, Activity label, and Timestamps. Also, case IDs are pseudonymized, and the activity labels are public. First, let us discuss privacy leakage *without* taking into account timestamps.

Proposition 5. *Let the event log L have a fixed constant timestamp value for all the entries. Let CT be the contingency table that corresponds to the event log L . Let M^{OV} be a mechanism that, for each count cell of the CT , samples (independently) noise z from Laplace distribution $Lap(1/\epsilon)$ and:*

- *Replicates the random cases that go through the DAFSA transition, which corresponds to the count cell with $z > 0$;*
- *Drop random cases from the event log that go through a DAFSA transition with count cell $z < 0$;*
- *Shuffles all cases and updates all case IDs before publishing the resulting event log.*

Let δ be the desired upper bound of the attacker succeeding in the goal h_1 . Then, it suffices to take

$$\epsilon = -\ln \left(\frac{P}{1-P} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\delta+P} - 1 \right) \right) ,$$

where $P = \frac{1-\delta}{2}$.

Proof. We need to show that manipulating the cases has the same privacy guarantees as to the addition of Laplace noise to the counts. Insertion and deletion of z cases work similarly to adding Laplace noise. The negative result is rounded up to 0 to fulfill the requirement R1. Such rounding is just post-processing, which is known to keep the DP property. However, L contains strictly more information than CT. For example, suppose the timestamps are different. In that case, the attacker can easily detect which cases are duplicates by seeking repeating timestamps. Having a fixed constant timestamp solves this problem. Another problem comes from new cases in the event log, e.g., they cannot be put into the end and cannot be issued easily identifiable case IDs. For example, if the real case IDs range from 0 to 10, and we start fake case IDs from 11, the attacker will clearly see which cases are duplicates. Shuffling and subsequent renaming of case IDs solve this problem. More formally, the final result is just a multiset of cases, equivalent to a count histogram of a corresponding CT. \square

In practice, we would like to avoid *undersampling* and only use *oversampling* to keep all the initial entries in the event log to fulfill the requirement R1.

Proposition 6. *Let the event log L have a fixed timestamp value for all the entries. Let CT be the contingency table that corresponds to the event log L . Let M^{OV} be a mechanism that, for each count cell of the CT , samples (independently) noise z from Laplace distribution $Lap(1/\epsilon)$ and:*

- *Inserts into L $|z|$ additional copies of any cases that have been included in that count cell;*
- *Shuffles all resulting cases and updates all case IDs before publishing the resulting event log.*

Let δ be the desired upper bound of the attacker succeeding in the goal h_1 . Then,

- *it suffices to take*

$$\epsilon = -2 \ln(b/c^2 - (\delta - 1)/(c \cdot b)) ,$$

where $c = \sqrt[3]{6}$ and $b = \sqrt[3]{\sqrt{3} \cdot \sqrt{2} \cdot \delta^3 + 21 \cdot \delta^2 - 48 \cdot \delta + 25 - 9 \cdot \delta + 9}$.

- a mechanism that adds noise $|z|$, where $z \leftarrow \text{Lap}(1/\epsilon)$, fulfills the requirement *R1*

Proof. For a mechanism M that adds only positive noise $|z|$ to the counts of the CT, it fulfills *R1* by design because it oversamples the cases, and it does not suppress any case. Oversampling the cases using Definition 3.9 keeps the same case variants as the input $\log L$. We can repeat the proof of Proposition 5 to show that privacy guarantees are as good as for a mechanism M that adds noise $|z|$ for $z \leftarrow \text{Lap}(1/\epsilon)$ to the count of CT constructed from L . It remains to prove which guarantees such noise addition would give. Let D_1 and D_2 be two neighboring databases that differ in the presence of one case. W.l.o.g. let D_1 have a smaller count than D_2 for the observed count cell. Suppose that the added noise instance is $|z| \geq 1$. In that case, the noisified output y can be obtained from both D_1 and D_2 . In particular, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\Pr[M(D_1) = y]}{\Pr[M(D_2) = y]} &= \frac{\exp(\epsilon \cdot (y - M(D_1)))}{\exp(\epsilon \cdot (y - M(D_2)))} \\ &= \exp(\epsilon \cdot (y - M(D_1) + y - M(D_2))) \\ &\leq \exp(\epsilon) . \end{aligned}$$

So the guessing advantage δ for $|z| \geq 1$ can be computed as in Proposition 5. However, for $|z| < 1$, the noisy value y produced by $M(D_1)$ will be *between* the true counts of D_1 and D_2 , and y could never be an output of $M(D_2)$ since we only add positive noise. The probability of getting $|z| \geq 1$ for Laplace noise is $CDF_{LAP}(1) - CDF_{LAP}(-1) = (1 - \frac{1}{2}\exp(-\epsilon)) - \frac{1}{2}\exp(-\epsilon) = 1 - \exp(-\epsilon)$. This means that, if ϵ is computed to achieve guessing advantage δ' with standard Laplace distribution as in Proposition 5, then the actual guessing advantage with one-sided Laplace distribution will be

$$\delta = \exp(-\epsilon) \cdot \delta' + (1 - \exp(-\epsilon)) . \quad (4)$$

Expressing δ from ϵ is more complicated. We need a solution that satisfies (4). From proposition 2, the maximum ϵ that achieves the upper bound δ is $\epsilon = -\ln\left(\frac{P}{1-P} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\delta'+P} - 1\right)\right)$ for $P = \frac{1-\delta'}{2}$. We can find a solution by substituting into (4) and using a numerical solver (in our case, Wolfram Alpha) to express ϵ through δ . It equals the quantity in the proposition statement. Also, the requirement *R1* is fulfilled.

One difference between adding noise to the counts and replicating cases is that repeating a case results in adding the same amount of noise to different count cells of the CT. In the worst case, the noise added to other cells may be precisely the same. In general, such a thing is not allowed in DP: e.g., if the attacker knows what the count of event A should be, and he notices that there are exactly 100 copies of A made, he may infer that there are 100 copies of B as well. That allows learning at most the *differences* between correlated counts. We note that, since we assume an attacker who knows the set of possible cases of an event \log anyway, he wants to learn which case the target individual belongs to (single

out the individual). In advance, the attacker knows that some prefixes/suffixes have the same frequency, as they belong to the same case variant. However, the attacker does not know the difference in prefixes/suffixes counts of different cases. Hence, we sample the noise independently for every oversampling step. \square

Now let us assume that we keep the timestamps as well. We need to add enough noise to the timestamps to prevent attacker success in h_2 , and h_1 , since timestamps may potentially leak which traces are real and which are not (oversampled). Let us start from h_2 .

First, we note that correlations between timestamps are difficult to handle in terms of guessing advantage. The main problem is that the effect of correlated times would greatly depend on how exactly they are correlated, and in some cases even a tiny leakage of t_2 may leak everything about t_1 . Here is a small example. Let t_1 in $\{0, 1\}$ and t_2 in $\{0, \dots, 1023\}$ be distributed uniformly. We have $P_1 = 1/2$, and $P_2 = 1/1024$. Suppose that, after seeing the noisy output, the attacker constrained his view of t_2 to $\{0, \dots, 511\}$. There are now 512 possible choices for t_2 , so $\delta = 1/512 - 1/1024 = 1/1024$, which is very small. However, when t_1 is the highest bit of t_2 , the value of t_1 is perfectly leaked. This particular correlation of times is unlikely in practice, but it demonstrates the problem in general.

To solve this issue, we convert a timestamp t_k to a time difference $dt_k := t_k - t_{k-1}$ of sequential events, which is the duration of time that an individual has spent in a transition from one event to the next one, and t_0 is the starting time st , which needs to be published as well to make it possible to reconstruct the actual timestamps. We leave the protection of starting times st an open issue. We can now assume that the values dt_k are independent for subsequent events and keep ϵ_k for the privacy of dt_k . We can obtain a bit stronger result for linearly correlated time differences (i.e., increasing duration of the first event by 1 minute increases every other event at most by 1 minute) scaling ϵ_k by the length of the trace. The following proposition tells how to protect the time differences.

Proposition 7. *Let M^T be a mechanism that, for each timestamp t_k , samples (independently) noise from the Laplace distribution $Lap(1/\epsilon)$ and adds it to t_k . Let r_k the maximum possible value of t_k . Let δ be the desired upper bound of the attacker succeeding in the goal h_2 with precision p . Then, it suffices to take*

$$\epsilon_k = -\frac{\ln\left(\frac{P_k}{1-P_k} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\delta+P_k} - 1\right)\right)}{m \cdot r_k},$$

where $P_k = CDF(t_k + p \cdot r_k) - CDF(t_k - p \cdot r_k)$, CDF is the probability density function of the distribution of times, and m is the length of the longest trace in L .

Proof. Similarly to Proposition 6, we can estimate an upper bound on the difference between the posterior and the prior probability of guessing an attribute ranging between 0 and 1 by

$$\delta = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\epsilon_k \cdot r_k)^{\frac{1-P_k}{P_k}}} - P_k,$$

which can be reversed to

$$\epsilon_k = -\frac{\ln\left(\frac{P_k}{1-P_k} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\delta+P_k} - 1\right)\right)}{r_k}.$$

The quantity P_k is defined as the probability of a value being in the interval $[t_k - p \cdot r_k, t_k + p \cdot r_k]$. Proposition 2 proves that the above value of ϵ is the maximum within the upper bound δ . Similarly to Proposition 6, if CDF of time distributions is unknown, it is safe to take P_k that minimizes the ϵ_k (and hence maximizes the amount of noise), which is $P_k = \frac{1-\delta}{2}$ for all k .

This was about leakage for a single published timestamp. We could keep ϵ_k the same for an entire L if different times are not correlated. If the times are linearly correlated, then, by the sequential composition of DP, we need to divide ϵ_k by the length of the longest trace m . \square

Let us now consider the attacker’s goal h_1 . It should be difficult for an attacker to tell whether an observed case is a true or fake one (i.e., generated during replication). Therefore, we add timestamp-specific details to the oversampling algorithm. The safest solution would be to assign to the replicated case a completely new timestamp, sampled *randomly* from the distribution of times. If we compute a discrete distribution over a set of certain fixed timestamps based on the dataset, then any new timestamp would just be sampled from the set of existing ones.

The problem here is that we assume a powerful attacker who knows the exact set of discrete timestamps that are in the dataset. However, such prior knowledge may already leak the true counts. For example, if the times 0.01, 10.01, and 99.67 come with equal probability, then it is easy for an attacker to detect duplicates such as three identical instances of 10.01. Hence, we need to assume a weaker attacker. Intuitively, we want to smooth the distribution of times to make it continuous, e.g., assume that times come from the intervals $[0, 2]$, $[8, 12]$, and $[98, 100]$. We note that such prior knowledge would be more realistic than knowing a precise discrete distribution. We can proceed as follows:

- We replicate a *randomly chosen* case among those affecting the CT count under observation, ensuring that the distribution of times in the oversampled L is the same as in the initial L .
- When adding noise $|z|$ to a timestamp, we scale it by $|z|$ (divide ϵ by $|z|$), ensuring that up to $|z|$ copies of the same timestamp instance do not leak more than a single copy would do.

The sampled noise will make it hard to distinguish e.g., whether it was a duplicated timestamp 10.01 or an actual timestamp 11.1067. The attacker can detect the duplicates if he manages to remove noise from the timestamps. The hardness of this is parametrized by δ and p . When adding noise to the timestamp, we need to set the precision parameter p in h_2 in such a way that, e.g., if the attacker says that the value is 2, this is as good as if he said that the value is exactly 0.01, the value 8 is as good as 10.01, and so on. In our example, it would

suffice to take $p = 0.02$ to make the guesses from an approximated continuous distribution as good as from the discrete distribution, but a larger p could lead to higher privacy guarantees.

We assume the event log publisher selects real p . We cannot recommend a particular “good” value for the quantity p . As in the case of CT counts, taking the worst-case prior $P = \frac{1-\delta}{2}$ would work for any distribution of timestamps within the bounds.

Let us now summarize the propositions above into a single theorem.

Theorem 1. *Let L be an event log. Let CT be the contingency table that corresponds to the event log L . Assume that the timestamps are converted to time differences dt_k between sequential events in L and the starting time st of a trace. We will further use notation t_k for both dt_k and st .*

Let M^T be a mechanism that, for each timestamp t_k , samples (independently) noise from the Laplace distribution $Lap(1/\epsilon_k)$ and adds it to t_k . Let r_k the maximum possible value of t_k .

Let M^{OV} be a mechanism that, for each count cell of the CT , samples (independently) noise z from Laplace distribution $Lap(1/\epsilon_{cnt})$ and:

- *Inserts into L $|z|$ additional copies of any cases that have been included in that count cell;*
- *Shuffles all resulting cases and updates all case IDs before publishing the resulting event log.*

Let δ_1 be the desired upper bound of the attacker's advantage in succeeding in the goal h_1 after observing the event log $M^T(M^{OV}(L))$. Then, it suffices to take

$$\epsilon_{cnt} = -2\ln(b/c^2 - (\delta - 1)/(c \cdot b)) ,$$

where $c = \sqrt[3]{6}$ and $b = \sqrt[3]{\sqrt{3} \cdot \sqrt{2} \cdot \delta^3 + 21 \cdot \delta^2 - 48 \cdot \delta + 25 - 9 \cdot \delta + 9}$.

Let δ_2 be the desired upper bound of the attacker's advantage in succeeding in the goal h_2 with precision p after observing the event log $M^T(M^{OV}(L))$. Then, it suffices to take

$$\epsilon_k = -\frac{\ln\left(\frac{P_k}{1-P_k} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\delta_2+P_k} - 1\right)\right)}{|z| \cdot r_k} ,$$

where $|z|$ is the total number of duplicates of the record k obtained due to oversampling, $P_k = CDF(t_k + p \cdot r_k) - CDF(t_k - p \cdot r_k)$, and CDF is the probability density function of the distribution of times. If CDF is not known, we can take $P_k = \frac{1-\delta}{2}$ for all k .

Proof. We take the value of ϵ_{cnt} from Proposition 6, and the value for ϵ_k from Proposition 7. Since a single case oversampling ends up in $|z|$ copies of every timestamp of the replicated case, we need to scale the ϵ_k of all events of the corresponding case by $|z|$.

2 Evaluation Supplementary Material

2.1 Dataset Selection

Table 1 shows the selected event logs and their descriptive statistics.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Event Logs

event log	# Traces	# Tasks	# Events	# Edges	Case Variant	Trace Length		Case Duration		
						Min	Max	Min	Max	Avg
<i>BPI12</i> [5]	13087	23	262200	116	4366	3	175	1.85 s	4.51 m	1.23 w
<i>BPI13_i</i> [16]	7554	4	65533	16	1511	1	123	inst.	2.11 y	1.73 w
<i>BPI14_i</i> [2]	46616	39	466737	497	22632	1	178	14 s	1.07 y	5.07 d
<i>BPI15₁</i> [3]	1199	398	52217	495	1170	2	101	8.56 h	4.07 y	3.15 m
<i>BPI17</i> [6]	31509	24	1202267	181	3942	10	180	3.35 m	9.4 m	3.13 w
<i>BPI18</i> [8]	43809	14	2514266	499	28457	24	2973	3.74 m	2.77 y	11.03 m
<i>BPIC19</i> [7]	251734	42	1595923	498	11973	1	990	2 ms	70.33 y	2.35 m
<i>BPI20_r</i> [4]	7065	51	86581	500	1478	3	90	12.61 h	3.26 y	2.87 m
<i>CCC19</i> [15]	20	29	1394	149	20	52	118	11 m	1.01 d	1.73 h
<i>CredReq</i> [1]	10035	8	150525	9	1	15	15	3.5 h	5 d	22 h
<i>Hospital</i> [14]	1143	624	150291	903	981	1	1814	inst.	3.17 y	1.06 y
<i>Sepsis</i> [13]	1050	16	15214	115	846	3	185	2.03 m	1 y	4 w
<i>Traffic</i> [12]	150370	11	561470	77	231	2	20	3 d	12 y	11 m
<i>Unrine.</i> [9]	1650	10	6973	25	50	2	35	10.1 m	2.32 y	3.7 w

2.2 Folder Organization

The attached folder to this PDF contains the anonymized event logs and the error metrics. The error metrics are presented as a CSV file, called “combined_error_metrics.csv”. The anonymized event logs are organized into folders. The high-level folders is the δ values for the anonymized event logs. The sub-folders represent the value of the precision parameter p . The naming convention of the files are of the form “e_anonymized_s1_t.s2.s3.s4”. “s1” represents the event log name. “s2” represents the value of the precision parameter. “s3” represents the value of the δ parameter. “s4” represents the iteration. The ϵ values used for every event and every case variant is stored in the event log. The event attribute “epsilon_per_event” represents the ϵ used to anonymize the time component of this event. The case attribute “epsilon_per_trace” represents the ϵ value used to anonymize the frequency of all the instances of this case variant.

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